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PRESILIENT

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and innovation: building post-pandemic resilient communities in Indonesia.

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Executive Summary

This report is the result of a Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise conducted within the PRESILIENT project with the aim of investigating the role of the informal economy in building post-pandemic resilience in the Global South. The HS activity aimed to identify economic sectors most affected by the COVID-19 crisis, as well as those showing signs of adaptation, innovation, and recovery, with a particular focus on informal economic dynamics.

This Indonesia-focused report draws on qualitative and desk-based methods, including literature review, policy and media analysis, and grey literature, to investigate emerging socio-economic and political-economic trends in the country's informal sector during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Unlike other country reports that may rely on large-scale quantitative data or automated keyword mapping, this contribution offers an in-depth interpretive qualitative analysis grounded in political economy and environmental justice scholarship.

Key findings suggest that urban, service-oriented informal sectors—such as tourism, retail, and transport—were disproportionately impacted by the pandemic, leaving many informal workers and gig workers without income or social protection. Conversely, small-scale agriculture, despite its high level of informality, proved relatively resilient, absorbing displaced workers and demonstrating its role as a safety net during economic shocks. This report highlights the importance of local and community-based innovations, such as the use of digital platforms by MSMEs, and the emergence of social enterprises, ethical, and sustainability-related model, in supporting economic adaptation and recovery.

Keywords

Informal Economy, COVID-19 impact, Pandemic recovery, Informal Sector, Informality, Gig workers, Social protection, Community-based, Informal Worker, Informal Recycling Sector, Digital Platforms, Waste bank, Social Entrepreneurship, Social and Solidarity Economy, Business Model Innovation, Social Enterprises, Circular Economy, Multi-stakeholder approach, Just Transition

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Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Indonesian country-level contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The Horizon Scanning methodology, as defined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is a collective and comparative tool used to identify early signals, opportunities, and risks that may shape the future of informal economies in the Global South. The overarching aim is to trace which sectors declined or expanded in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and to identify those that could contribute to resilient and inclusive post-pandemic recovery pathways.

The HS exercise across PRESILIENT's 15-country network was designed to be flexible and adapted to the specificity of each context. While the general methodological protocol outlined the use of mixed methods and potential integration of bibliometric and quantitative trend analyses, each Early-Stage Researcher (ESR) was also encouraged to adapt the tools according to their disciplinary background and access to sources. In this case, the report builds on a qualitative analysis focusing on sectoral fluctuations and how local actors interpret, cope, or creatively adapt to external shocks and structural pressures.

In this Indonesian case, no large-scale statistical dataset or automated bibliometric analysis was used. Instead, it adopts a methodological approach centered on:

- A thematic review of literature, reports, and critical essays related to informality, livelihoods, and resilience in Indonesia.
- Analysis of grey literature, policy documents, and national and international development discourse.
- A comparative reading of media narratives and regional reports, actively including sources coming from non-conventional and independent media, which are often more attuned to grassroots perspectives and less filtered by institutional agendas.
- Engagement with political economy and environmental justice studies addressing sustainability transition and community-based circular economies.

This interpretive and grounded approach is consistent with PRESILIENT's epistemological stance, which doesn't reduce informality to a statistical anomaly to be corrected, recognizing it instead as a field of knowledge, agency, and innovation. As such, the report highlights the political and ethical dimensions of economic practices, where the informal economy is often tied to broader struggles for autonomy, dignity, global justice, and environmental sustainability. In this context, the findings contribute to a comparative understanding of post-pandemic dynamics and will inform the subsequent phases of the project, including expert-based Delphi surveys and case study development. They also offer policy-relevant insights by challenging dominant assumptions about formalization and proposing alternative economic imaginaries rooted in lived experience.

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Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the common research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also followed a structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. The data collection process was based on the identification and use of pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. In line with the shared methodological guidelines, the research drew on approximately 150 sources, comprising—where available—50 academic references, 50 media articles, and 50 grey literature or policy documents. These materials were selected through targeted searches, curated for relevance, and then closely read, coded, and interpreted in light of the researcher’s contextual knowledge and disciplinary perspective. Each step of this process—keyword selection, source collection, critical reading, and report drafting—is made explicit to reinforce methodological transparency. Although the emphasis in this Indonesian case is on qualitative approach, the report remains anchored in a systematic data-gathering process shared across the PRESILIENT network. This approach produces a robust analysis that reflects local realities and contributes to the broader comparative project.

Informal Economies in Indonesia: Socioeconomic Context

In Indonesia, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted nearly all major sectors of the economy, with several key industries experiencing severe declines. The five sectors most affected—manufacturing, wholesale and retail trade, transportation, accommodation, and services—collectively accounted for 41 percent of Indonesia’s economy in 2019 (Bodamaev, 2020). Among these, the tourism and hospitality industry faced the sharpest collapse, driven by social distancing measures and strict movement restrictions; in 2020, foreign tourist arrivals fell by 28.85 percent compared to 2019 (Atmojo & Fridayani, 2021). The transportation sector was similarly impacted, as mobility restrictions and reduced domestic travel demand—particularly in tourism-dependent regions such as Bali and Yogyakarta—led to significant economic losses (Halimatussadiyah et al., 2020).

Agricultural sector which has been largely relied on most people in Indonesia has showed a highest positive growth (9.5% quarter to quarter in 2020), compare to other sectors (Bodamaev, 2020). Despite the nature of informality in this sector, during shocks like pandemic, it shows the potential for accommodating workers who have been laid off (Malahayati et al., 2021). It is supported by recent data from Statistics Indonesia (BPS) reported that in 2023, more than 60% or 83.34 million people working in the informal sector, where in agriculture alone, nearly 89% of the workers were in employed informally.

Multiple factors heightened the vulnerability of Indonesia’s key economic sectors during the pandemic, particularly for workers and businesses in the informal economy. In tourism, the sector’s dependence on international mobility and its labor-intensive nature—employing 11 percent of Indonesia’s workforce in 2018 (Bodamaev, 2020)—left many informal workers and gig workers without income or social protection when operations stalled. The trade sector, including retail and small and medium enterprises (SMEs), faced similar challenges as physical store closures coincided with a rapid consumer shift toward e-commerce. Many MSMEs, especially informal and

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micro-enterprises, were forced into temporary shutdowns, struggled with cash shortages, and faced sharp revenue declines (ADB & Gojek, 2023). The manufacturing sector also experienced significant strain, as supply chain disruptions and declining demand forced companies to scale back production, leaving informal and contract-based workers particularly exposed (Sugianto et al., 2023).

Regional and Global Comparison

When comparing Indonesia with other countries in Asia, a similar pattern emerges. Countries such as Vietnam also saw MSMEs (micro, small, and medium enterprises) as a critical concern where they account for over 90 percent of firms, the majority operating informally. This small business showed notable resilience through rapid adoption of digital platforms, enabling some businesses to weather the crisis. Sector-specific impacts also reveal notable comparisons. In tourism, Indonesia experienced a medium level of disruption relative to other countries, with tourist arrivals plunging by more than 70 percent in 2020—devastating Bali’s local economy through widespread hotel closures and job losses. This mirrored severe tourism shocks in Vietnam, where the sector ranked as one of the most disrupted, while Zambia and Kenya also faced substantial declines in tourism-dependent regions.

Globally, On the macroeconomic level, economic and fiscal growth pressures were highly prevalent in both Indonesia and Zambia, as both countries struggled to stimulate their economies while maintaining fiscal sustainability amidst contracting GDP during the crisis. By comparison, these concerns were somewhat less pronounced in Vietnam and Kenya, where growth trajectories and fiscal pressures differed, though the balancing act between stimulus and debt was a shared challenge across the region.

Emerging Trends and Feedback

It is clear that during the pandemic, several sectors experienced surged as a result of restrictions which made people stay and working from home. In Indonesia, the digital adoption rise significantly among 99 percent of small medium enterprises transforming their operation during pandemic (Herman, 2021). Students and teachers have been forced to explore digitally enabled remote learning options, including EdTech solutions, due to school closures. The adoption of health technology apps for remote consultations has also reached unprecedented levels (World Bank, 2021). The financial technology apps also emerge, especially for short-term loan services which targeting low-income individuals who do not have access to commercial bank due to lack of collateral.

The consumer behavior also shifting towards e-commerce, enterprises gradually shifting from physical to digital sales by marketing and selling their products through online platform (ADB & Gojek, 2023). Some sectors have not been so affected include those providing certain medical goods and services, and less contact-intensive activities such as finance, education, communications, and telecommunications (Wihardja & Cunningham, 2021). The demand for ethical products also increases including in the halal industry. New business models and social enterprises also emerge, following with the trend on Environment, Social and Governance (ESG) topics and climate tech has increased its popularity in their investment (Tech in Asia, 2023). In the

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employment market landscape, the shift toward remote work and gig economy has been also increased.

Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). *PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (including Indonesia). It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). *Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

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